

THE MOST IMPORTANT METHODS OF CONTROLLING MONEY OUTSIDE THE BUDGET

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the most important methods of controlling extrabudgetary funds. The article is divided into two parts: the first part gives recommendations on the purpose and importance of extrabudgetary funds control, and the second part explains the most important methods of this control and gives recommendations on how to implement them.*

Keywords: *budget monitoring, important methods, external funds, review, financial control, public expenditure, expenditure analysis, financial transparency.*

Today, the global financial and economic crisis still has a negative impact on the economy of large developed countries. Despite all the measures taken to improve the situation during the past period, the growth rate and production are actually decreasing in most countries, and if this process continues, it will lead to a global recession, that is, it is predicted the economy will continue to decrease instead of increasing. In many developed countries, public debt and public budget deficits continue to increase amid uncertainty and various risks.

At the same time, complex problems related to the instability of the world's reserve currencies, a sharp decrease in the credit capacity of the financial and banking system, and a decrease in investment activity have a negative impact on the recovery and growth rates of the economy of many countries. In our country, in the future, planning the state budget for the medium term, focusing on the result when allocating funds to the budget, strengthening the revenue part of local budgets in the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, budgets of different levels while maintaining the social orientation of state budget expenditures tasks such as ensuring proportionality are envisaged.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev referring to the tax-budget policy, says: "Strict adherence to the tax-budget policy, fulfillment of the state's social obligations, the amount of wages, pensions, benefits and scholarships, financing of large investment projects and the strengthening of the country's defense capabilities are the most important. For the implementation of tasks, first of all, the Ministry of Finance currently creates conditions for the full formation of market relations in front of the tax system of our country, as well as providing the state budget with funds and supporting priority economic activities through taxes is required".

At the center of the changes in the state finance reform are the formation of the state budget and the more effective use of its funds, the prevention of factors affecting the growth of the budget deficit, and at the same time the observance of budget disciplines in the process of using budget funds and in this, there are issues of strengthening financial control and, in addition, increasing the importance of the state budget in the socio-economic development of the country through the formation of an effective financial control system.

It is important to establish effective control over extra-budgetary funds to ensure transparency and accountability in financial management. Recommendations on the purpose and importance of extrabudgetary controls provide valuable insight into why these controls are necessary. In addition, the explanation of methods of controlling extrabudgetary funds and

recommendations for their implementation are essential for organizations to effectively manage their funds and prevent misuse or theft.

When it comes to monitoring and evaluating external funds, there are several important methods to consider. Each approach has its own advantages and limitations, so it is important to understand them thoroughly before implementing them. Some key techniques in this area are:

Results-based evaluation: This method aims to evaluate the actual results achieved through funding through predetermined results. This is very important to understand the impact of the budget on the achievement of the intended objectives.

Performance audit: A performance audit conducted by independent auditors evaluates the effectiveness and efficiency of budget expenditures. This method helps identify areas for improvement and ensure accountability.

Financial Statement Analysis: Financial statement analysis provides insight into the financial health of a project or organization. It helps in tracking costs, identifying discrepancies and maintaining transparency.

Stakeholder consultation: Involving stakeholders in the monitoring and evaluation process is essential to understand their perspectives and tailor the budget to their needs. This increases transparency and builds trust.

Benchmarking: By comparing budget allocations and spending patterns with similar projects or organizations, evaluators can identify best practices, trends, and areas for improvement.

These are some of the important methods of monitoring and evaluation of external funds. Each method plays a crucial role in ensuring transparency, accountability and efficient use of resources.

The formation of budget funds and their rational use cannot be achieved without the formation of an effective control system. It is known that one of the main stages of the budget process is the financial control of the state. Financial control is a component of control activities implemented in our country. To solve this problem, it is recommended to create a monitoring and reporting system in advance, in which private programs and platforms can be used to automatically collect and sort data. These systems can be used to better organize financial control, monitor and analyze data. This method can effectively help in the formation of budget funds and their rational use.

Budget control is carried out by state financial control bodies in order to identify, eliminate and prevent violations of budget legislation by financial control objects. A number of normative documents are being adopted in order to improve their activities.

Along with the progress made as a result of the measures being implemented, there are still problems in this area that are waiting for their solution. In particular, as a result of the final control carried out by financial control bodies, cases of misuse of budget funds are constantly being identified.

The income of budget organizations from the sale of goods (works, services) to the development fund of the budget organization is determined as a positive difference between the proceeds from the sale of goods (works, services) and the costs of their production.

Effective budgeting, implementation and control of funds serves to ensure targeted spending. For this reason, the budget execution process requires reliable information. In this case, accounting is the main source of information, and its organization is considered economically important. Reasonable and effective use of budget funds in the conditions of economic reform,

effective organization of financing is considered one of the urgent issues. Creating, implementing and controlling budgets effectively and efficiently serve to ensure targeted spending. For this reason, there is a need for reliable information during budget implementation. In this case, accounting is the main source of information, and its organization is economically important. In the context of economic reforms, rational and effective use of budget funds, effective organization of financing of budget organizations is considered one of the urgent issues. Budget organizations are considered the main consumer of budget funds, organizer of the expenses of the State budget and are financed from the budget based on the cost estimate. In addition, the budget organization shall, in accordance with the law, receive from the budget the sources of organization and directions of use of extra-budgetary funds, carry out expenses within the framework of estimates for extra funds. The cost estimate includes the distribution of expenses of the fourth group by items of expenses, as well as the list of groups of goods (works, services) that are primarily purchased from small business entities for state needs is attached. Cost estimates of budget organizations and recipients of budget funds are drawn up in two copies, and in triplicate for budget organizations and recipients of budget funds under the control of the allocator of budget funds.

The article describes the most important methods of controlling extrabudgetary funds. These methods are very important for average people and are recommended to be followed in the initial stages. Currently, the important methods considered to control extra-budgetary funds are, for example, complete accounting, control of funds handling processes, review of expenses and never losing funds. These methods are essential in maintaining legal order and supporting emerging funds in the right direction.

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